

The application of IM-tools by the Dutch government.

**Issam
el Bouazzati**

i.elbouazzati
@tilburguniversity.
edu

**Bertrand
Gakuba**

b.gakuba@til
burguniversity.edu

**Ouassim
Nnafie**

o.nnafie@tilb
urguniversity.edu

**Hicham
Khallouk**

h.khallouk@ti
lburguniversity.edu

**Ayyoub
el Moussaoui**

a.elmoussaoui
@tilburguniversity.
edu

ABSTRACT

This article is mainly about the contribution of Information Management to the changed organizational goals that the Ministry of Health aims to reach. This concerns the organizational goals as a result of the COVID-19 crisis. Entire industries will have to adapt to "the new normal." Information Management can play a vital role in driving this change and in achieving new business goals. This article will mainly focus on the contribution of the Coronamelder to the changes that the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport is going through since the Corona crisis. The subject is approached from various sub-disciplines, namely from Business Process Integration, IT Governance & Strategic Sourcing and the field of Cybersecurity. Existing literature will be examined for this. In the discussion, the barriers are mentioned that hold back a change, as well as the success factors. Ultimately, the main question will be answered and the effect of the contribution of IM to organizational changes in government bodies will be described. It is also zoomed out here and the result is drawn in a broader context.

Keywords

Ministry of VWS, Coronamelder, Organizational change, Covid-19, Business model, Information Management, Business Process Integration. IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing, Cybersecurity.

INTRODUCTION

It will not have escaped anyone that the world has been hit by a pandemic in the past year that no one saw coming. The consequences of the spread of the COVID-19 virus are immense. These negative consequences can be seen everywhere. Entire industries have (almost) come to a standstill, jobs have been lost and companies have had to change their business model in a short time. This

applies to both the commercial and public sectors, which this article will be particularly focused on.

This study will examine how the Ministry of Public Health, Welfare and Sport as an organization had to adapt to the corona crisis in order to provide its customers, in this case the Dutch people, with added value. This research will specifically focus on the contribution of Information Management to this organizational change. Because it is essentially a medical crisis, the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport is the driving force when it comes to protecting the people against the virus. Originally, the ministry's main task was to stimulate healthy behavior ("Organisatie ministerie van Volksgezondheid, Welzijn en Sport"). However, if we follow current events, we can conclude that the core task has changed in protecting the vulnerable groups from COVID-19 and at the same time mitigating the virus. The contribution of Information Management to this change will be explored in this study. This concerns changes in operational processes such as tactical and strategic changes.

The past year has shown how important it is to be agile as a company. If a company cannot keep up with changing trends, it is difficult for an organization to have a sustainable existence. The relevance of this research is therefore also in the application of technology in organizations to make processes more efficient and agile, so that changes can be made quickly if necessary.

RESEARCH

Objective

It is currently unclear to what extent the application of technology can provide a balance between effectiveness on the one hand and safety on the other. In this case, this is investigated on the basis of a case that zooms in on the use of the Coronamelder. This involves collecting and storing data from users (Coronamelder). The more data is used, the more intelligence can be created. On the

other hand, the underlying software is provided by *Google Apple Exposure Notification Framework* (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens). This is an American Tech giant who may also be able to get hold of the data. The question then arises of what happens to it. Since this includes medical data, this is an extra sensitive topic.

Approach

In order to gather the information that we have intended, a number of intermediate steps must be completed. First of all, it will be investigated what the processes are within the Ministry of VWS. Next, it will zoom in on the CoronaMelder and describe its use and usefulness. Subsequently, the contribution of the Coronamelder to the mission of the Ministry is discussed, as well as the contribution it makes to the change of the organization as a whole and the individual processes. In this way, this should form a case study to be able to answer the following research question:

How can an Information System e.g. an application contribute to reach the new goals that the Ministry of VWS aims to reach?

In the analysis, the case study will be discussed in order to ultimately be able to provide an overall answer to the research question in the conclusion. In order to gather the necessary information, use will mainly be made of literature accessible online. These are scientific articles and publications from the Ministry of VWS.

GOVERNMENT & PUBLIC SERVICE

In this section we introduce the sector Government & Public service, with the focus on the ministry of VWS. Not only private companies but also the public sector had to make organizational adjustments due to Covid-19. Worldwide the World Health Organization (WHO) plays a critical central role during the pandemic. Members of the United Nations follow the guidelines set up by the WHO. The WHO works closely with global experts, governments and partners to rapidly expand scientific knowledge on this new virus, to track the spread and virulence of the virus, and to provide advice to countries and individuals on measures to protect health and prevent the spread of this outbreak (UN News, 2020).

Quick thinking

Prior to the pandemic, public service and public servants were most likely used to work based on routines in a predictable and regulated atmosphere. However in regard to the pandemic this mindset had to change into quick thinking, instant creativity and innovation, especially in vulnerable environments for instance healthcare.

Ministry of VWS

For this research we decided to aim our attention specifically on the ministry of VWS. As previously mentioned, this organization's responsibilities consist of stimulating healthy behavior, strengthening the social infrastructure & enabling everybody to do sports. The highest function of this ministry is the Secretary-General. At the moment Hugo de Jonge holds the position of Secretary-General. He's responsible for leading several entities which fall under the ministry of VWS. Together with prime minister Rutte, they frequently hold press conferences about the coronavirus in order to update the citizens on current trends. Its total workforce counts 4424 full time equivalents. In order to cope with the Covid-19 pandemic, the department installed the National Consortium Tools also known as LCH. Its goal is to purchase sufficient personal protective equipment and medical devices of the correct quality as quickly as possible, (e.g.) mouth masks, gloves and aprons. In the LCH, healthcare providers, distribution companies and producers have joined forces to become stronger and prevent mutual competition between healthcare providers (Rijksoverheid, 2020).

The National Coordination Team Diagnostic Chain (LCDK) was set up by the Ministry of VWS to map out and increase the Dutch testing capacity. The LCDK coordinates the upscaling of the testing capacity for corona and facilitates collaboration within the diagnostic chain. The LCDK uses weekly requests to make an inventory of the current test capacity of the laboratories and the stocks of scarce materials at the suppliers. Furthermore, the LCDK collects data about the expected demand for tests from the IT system and the forecasts from the RIVM. The LTC and LCDK are good examples of connecting several organisations to tackle the Covid-19 pandemic as a unit. The role of information management in order to reach an effective collaboration is very important. The details of the corona detector application will be further explained in the following sections (Rijksoverheid, 2020).

ANALYSIS

2.1 IT governance and strategic sourcing

The crisis surrounding COVID-19 has clearly shown that the government must also be able to deal dynamically with disruptive events. All disruptive digital changes have presented the government with both opportunities and challenges. An important aspect and part of minimizing the spread of the COVID-19 virus is mapping the presence of the virus. In this, the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport has made optimal use of the current developments surrounding digitalization. The crisis has resulted in the government having to implement disruptive changes in IT facilities and organization. These current and future changes will be discussed on the basis of the five IT decision domains (Alreemy et al, 2016).

IT principles

The way of doing business between non-profit organizations, in this particular case 'the government', and profitable businesses is very different. At first, the customers of the government are the citizens of the country. When you deal with the citizens as 'customers' then the accessibility should be high and transparent for everyone. Also, it must be user friendly for the customers and easy to understand and operate for all kinds of different people as there are a lot of differences between the citizens. On the other hand, the government will deal with a lot of personal information and data of the citizens. This leads to the fact that the government must operate in a way which makes sure that the obtained data/information and the processing of this must be very secure, private and transparent; this is of very high importance because when personal information, in this case personal information about the concerned citizen regarding the COVID-19 data, of the citizens are leaked, hacked, etc. this can lead to unpleasant consequences for both the citizens and the government as well. Briefly, the government and the IT used to implement the government services and applications must take these '*IT Principles*' into account as the government is, eventually, responsible for her citizens and the safety and wellbeing of her citizens (Alexiou, 2020).

IT architecture

The government has been working on the current trend of digitalization and its integration into their processes for years. For example, the government already works with digital personal data and health apps. The government must take into account the security and privacy of these personal data. The app around the Coronamelder will mainly be based on data obtained from users

and will have to make observing the security and privacy of this data a priority. The current MedMij-rules and online identification will, for example, be able to contribute enormously to standardizing and securing these processes. Also the collection and processing of the data obtained by the app must take place in a standardized manner. Using a standardized process in obtaining data leads to efficiency and a more effective guarantee of security (Alexiou, 2020).

IT infrastructure

The government will use an existing underlying software developed by Apple and Google. Outsourcing the development of the software to Apple and Google poses challenges. The Exposure Notification API application is based on giving random codes to phones and uses Bluetooth Low Energy to indicate whether someone has been infected with the COVID-19 virus in your area. Giving and constantly changing random codes to a mobile device ensures that the anonymity of the usage is guaranteed. The application does not register who you are or where you are. It only deals with matching the associated codes that are sent to a central service to send a warning message if you may have been close to an infected person (Alexiou, 2020).

IT Business application needs

When developing the Coronamelder application, the government had to take into account the public and the purpose for which it serves. The application should have a clear, accessible design as the use of the application is intended for the entire population. In addition, the government will have to deal with an enormous bulk of data and obtaining the data will have to lead to simple processing and interpretation thereof. The disruption and urgency associated with the COVID-19 virus also requires data that can be analyzed easily and quickly. Due to the urgency of the development of the application and software, using an existing software and process is the best option. Taking an existing software and process into use will increase the priority of security and privacy over personal data. This includes the processing, storage and control of the acquired personal data. Security and privacy will therefore have to be managed by the government. In doing so, use can be made of the experience and standardization from current processes (Alexiou, 2020).

IT investment and prioritization

When setting up the application, urgency must be taken into account when considering the size of the investment. The current situation regarding the COVID-19 virus requires clarity and support that the Coronamelder can offer. The investment must mainly lie in the development of the application. There must be a priority of focus on investing in security and privacy, as well as creating a clear and self-explanatory application (Alexiou, 2020).

2.2 BPI

Business Process Integration (BPI) can be defined as the techniques and mechanisms for managing the movement of data, and the invocation of processes in the correct and proper order to support the management and execution of common processes that exist in and between applications (Lelli, F, 2020). The key processes within this definition can be Finance, Marketing, Human Resources and innovation. Within these processes, BPI is being used in order to manage the movement of data to support the management and the ongoing processes within an organization. The situation of the government regarding managing the movement of data before the COVID-crisis can be described as improving the sharing, combining and analyzing of data within the so called Data Agenda Overheid (Digitaleoverheid, 2019). This is an agenda which describes how to continuously improve datafication. The main focus is to solve problems by working data-driven. This is being done by working systematically and investing in knowledge, education and contacts in the data and business-world in order to create a broad and clear view of how to manage data and how to process this data in meaningful solutions for social-cultural problems which the government is facing.

After COVID-19, the process of managing the movement of data became different as the crisis is having a huge impact on society and the government. Data is being used to create more certainty towards the society and also for working on solutions with data-driven initiatives. With the announcement of the COVID-19 application, a lot of people are scared and uncertain about sharing their information and data to the government. This will be a big challenge for the government which needs to communicate very clearly about the impact and the use of this data. The skeptical voice of the people needs to be turned in to trust and reliance on the capabilities and the motives of the government. This may also include communication about the privacy and security of their information. Also managing the huge amounts of data which are currently being produced in a short amount of time will be a challenge. Processing and managing the COVID-

data will be difficult as it needs to be analyzed in order to create meaningful solutions and opportunities.

A new process that may need to be implemented is a tracking process in order to make the suggested application work. A challenge that may occur with this challenge is that society will resist against the thought that the government is following them and tracking with who they have been in contact with. This challenge is in close contact with the privacy issue that many people are experiencing with the new corona epidemic. This challenge needs to be overcome by communicating very clearly with the population by explaining and sharing the motives and the necessity and most importantly be transparent about the situation and the process that is going on.

The government needs to face the mentioned challenges in order to execute the key processes that exist in a correct way and to manage the movement of data in the best way possible.

2.3 Cybersecurity

To emphasize, currently we are living in a crisis, the implementation of the application 'corona melder app' comes forth from the attempt of the public sector/government trying to get an image and estimation of the citizens infected with the virus and where an infected person current location is so other citizens will be alarmed. Every phone with the application is subject to potential risks also because of the fact that remote electronic devices in general are carrying many challenges in cybersecurity. This application will use a lot of personal data (information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person and his or her creditations) and data transportation of the citizens/users. If hackers breach these information which expose other personal details of people (other information than corona-related data) can scare people away from using the application. This application is used on mobile devices. The risks that come along this type of data obtaining is sensitive to security breaches by hackers. The processes will only be accepted and trusted if the depth of the security is transparent enough and applicable to the users/citizens. Mobile devices connecting to networks (in this case the networks of application and the government) and the increased migration of critical data processing and storage in the databases of the storages of the application and government increase the possibility of cyberattacks of hackers to gain personal information of the citizens using the 'corona melder app' (Drew, 2012). These hacks can occur in or between the layers between the layers of processing, data and technical infrastructure.

The increasing of potential cyber attacks is possible of many reasons; hackers can make us of ransomware techniques that lock the systems and databases, while doing this the hackers have time to hack the personal data and they have the power to release the so-called 'lock' until they have reached their goal or until, for example, the hackers are paid for the release of the 'lock'. The data that can be retrieved for the hacks can obtain sufficient information for the hackers as the application can gain more data than what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed; thus, the possibility of cyber breached need to be minimalized.

As the pandemic grew exponentially in a small time, there is/was little time for security testing of the application; the developers of the application could have missed a lot of security restrictions and measures amid the pressure from the government to get the application built as soon as possible as developers need to put solutions in place as quick as possible.

Briefly, the application is an attractive target for hackers as they can gain information regarding secret health information about citizens and government officials or other targets. Also, as the government is able to use the information gained from the application might also collect more information than needed or keep the information stored longer than needed for purposes unrelated to the pandemic makes it more attractive for hackers which creates more fear under the people using the application.

A possible solution can be the creation of an underlying software that saves the information on the phones of the users instead of transporting the information to the servers of the government. This is better for the security against cyber breaches and also better for privacy matters because there will be no data transportation to central databases of the government which limits the possibility for hackers. This can provide a solution for the problems described above. But on the other hand, this solution can limit the usefulness of the information for the public sector and the government. The government, if intended to use the solution, must have to incur huge investment costs.

DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis that has been made within this report, there are some barriers that hold back a digital transformation. As mentioned earlier, privacy issues are one of the biggest issues that people experience with digital transformation. Communication within this matter is very important in order to keep the people updated on everything that is happening with their data. Another barrier is maintaining the huge amounts of data that is being processed with the new COVID-19 pandemic.

The success factors that make digital transformation contribute to organizational performance can be described as having a clear strategic plan to implement the different processes of digitalization. Also being transparent about everything that is happening within the process of digital transformation towards society is very important in order to succeed and to actually contribute to improve organizational performance.

A short term investment in an application that will likely not have the desired spread of the COVID-19 virus. This will probably have to do with the as yet unfamiliarity of the application and not building it into the application. The importance of the application will have to be made known to the population in the introduction phase in order to achieve a desired result. In the long run, if the confidence and awareness of the application has increased to generate a better outcome, a desired outcome of the application is to actively use it. Digitizing and automating the processes by the government will probably lead to a more efficient and effective result through the application in the short and long term. However, the cybersecurity of the application must be taken into account as well as the security and privacy of the active users. Help and intervention from external companies can be considered in this regard.

CONCLUSION

The Covid 19 pandemic has affected the whole world, especially governments and the public sector will have to adapt quickly. The Dutch government, specifically the Ministry of VWS, has tried to tackle this problem through a form of digital transformation. The Coronamelder application has been designed in order to track users who may have been in contact with the coronavirus.

The implementation of this application has been analysed from three perspectives, IT governance, business process integration and cyber security. This resulted in several useful insights, as to which possible risks and opportunities the government will face when they decide to launch the Coronamelder application.

Overall, we found that information systems can contribute to registering and plausible reduce the number of Covid-19 cases. However this can only be reached by carefully designing, implementing, monitoring & assessing the developments of the current pandemic and digital trends.

The biggest hurdle is probably the scepticism from citizens regarding the use of personal data within the application. The usefulness of Coronamelder heavily depends on its sum of users, the greater the number of users, the more valuable data that can be retrieved by the application. Transparency from the public sector will be key in order to gain the trust from its citizens. The lack of previous research studies regarding this topic, as well as the lack of data collection were found to be limitations during the research. In order to build the literature of work, future researchers are advised to collect more data on this subject.

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